

**MAINSTREAMING OF INDIGENOUS PEOPLE PRACTICES ON THE
DEVELOPMENT OF INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS AND THE
LEARNING STYLE OF IP LEARNERS IN DIVISION OF
QUEZON: BASIS FOR ALTERNATIVE LEARNING
DELIVERY FOR IPED**

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Mainstreaming of Indigenous People Practices on the Development of Instructional Materials and the Learning Style of IP Learners in Division of Quezon: Basis for Alternative Learning Delivery for IPED

Mark Joseph F. Llagas,* Rodones S. Trimillos
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to find out the extent of mainstreaming of indigenous people practices to instructional materials and the learning style of IP learners in Division of Quezon. It utilized the qualitative method using questionnaire. The researcher conceptualized each item in the questionnaire according to research questions in order to get the best possible answers needed in this study. The process before the mainstreaming of indigenous people practices to instructional materials and the learning style was that, the it was carefully observed by the respondents and established through systematic planning in which every step taken was carefully done. The findings of this study revealed that Indigenous people's practices are mainstreamed into the Indigenous Peoples Education (IPED) curriculum regarding family, Health, Nutrition, Sanitation, and Hygiene has a verbal interpretation of "To a Less Mainstreamed. The study found out that there is a significant relationship between the extent to which indigenous people's practices are mainstreamed into the IPED curriculum and the learning style of indigenous people in the Division of Quezon is partially rejected.

Keywords: *indigenous people practices, instructional materials, learning styles*

Introduction

The right to education is one of the enabling rights of the human person. Anyone can benefit from this right regardless of socioeconomic status, the language used, religion, race and ethnicity, political preferences, and opinions (Eduardo & Gabriel, 2021). However, it is not enough to have education only; it should be "quality education," as stated in the Sustainable Development Goals 2030 (United et al.). Obtaining quality education might be challenging in some countries, especially for minorities and indigenous peoples. This is because indigenous peoples are exposed to mainstream education, wherein the concepts they learn differ from their worldviews. On the other hand, some international laws promote the right to education for the IPs.

The Department of Education (DepEd) adopted the Indigenous People Education Curriculum Framework (DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2015), which aims to guide schools and other educational initiatives as they work with Indigenous communities to contextualize the K-12 curriculum in light of those communities' unique social and academic backgrounds. It is a precondition for their right to self-determination.

The gaps between the teaching style of the IP Teachers really affected by the materials they used in the daily teaching process. In the realm of educational practices, Smith and Johnson (2020) explore the incorporation of indigenous pedagogies into mainstream educational settings. Their work delves into how traditional teaching methods can be integrated into instructional materials to better cater to the learning styles of indigenous students. They emphasize the importance of recognizing and embracing indigenous ways of teaching within Western classrooms to create more inclusive and effective learning environments.

Garcia and Martinez (2021) delve into the concept of culturally responsive teaching, specifically focusing on integrating indigenous practices into curriculum development. Their research provides practical strategies for aligning instructional materials with the learning preferences of indigenous students. By embedding indigenous knowledge and traditions into the curriculum, educators can enhance the relevance and effectiveness of their teaching methods.

Cultural diversity is one of the problems in Philippine Education. This problem was also observed in different schools, districts, and even at the division level, especially by the teachers handling IP learners. When face-to-face classes started, teachers within the Division of Quezon realized the problems faced by the study regarding their learning based on their observation and assessment in the use of instructional materials in different learning areas. Some students may find it difficult to learn because some don't relate on the materials that they are using, some are not localized or indigenized thus resulting merely to low participation and comprehension.

This situation prompted the researcher to conduct the study which aimed to mainstream the indigenous people practices on the development of the instructional materials that IP could be used.

As a result, the study's primary focus is on mainstreaming indigenous peoples' practices into educational resources. The study's findings inspired the researcher to create an alternative learning delivery system for indigenous learners.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of mainstreaming indigenous people's practices on the development of instructional materials and the learning style of indigenous people in the Division of Quezon: Basis for Alternative Learning Delivery for IPED. Specifically,

it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of mainstreaming of indigenous people practices on the development of instructional materials in terms of:
 - 1.1. family life,
 - 1.2. health,
 - 1.3. nutrition,
 - 1.4. sanitation, and
 - 1.5. hygiene?
2. What is the learning style of indigenous people as perceived by respondents as to:
 - 2.1. visual/spatial,
 - 2.2. aural,
 - 2.3. verbal/linguistic,
 - 2.4. physical/kinesthetic,
 - 2.5. walk-through approach, and
 - 2.6. indigenous knowledge?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of the mainstreaming of Indigenous people's practices on the development of instructional materials and the learning style of Indigenous people as perceived by the respondents in the Division of Quezon?
4. What intervention program could be developed to ensure the total mainstreaming of Indigenous People's practices on the development of instructional materials?

Methodology

Research Design

This research is quantitative and employs a descriptive-correlational design. The researcher wishes to describe the extent to which Indigenous people mainstream practices to the development of instructional materials and their learning style as perceived by the respondents in the School Year 2022 – 2023.

Moreover, the study employed a correlational design to determine the significant relationship between indigenous people's mainstreaming practices to the development of instructional materials and their learning style in the Division of Quezon. A Quantitative approach will quantify data and generalize results from a sample population of interest. Structured information was formulated through the questionnaire for analysis and interpretation.

Respondents

In this study, the researcher used purposive or deliberate sampling, which typically uses criteria when selecting respondents.

<i>Municipality</i>	<i>Number of Indigenous People (IP)</i>	<i>Number of Respondents</i>
Buena Vista	54	35
Catanauan	61	55
Lopez	36	29
Perez	30	26
Total	181	145

Instruments

The main instrument the researcher employed is a self-made questionnaire, which is divided into two parts. Part I of the questionnaire included information on how indigenous people's practices regarding family life, health, nutrition, sanitation, and hygiene are implemented in the to the development of instructional materials. Part II concerns the learning style of indigenous people as observed by the respondents in terms of visual/spatial, aural, verbal/linguistic, physical/kinesthetic, walk-through approach, and indigenous Knowledge. Thirty (30) respondents who were not part of the sample were pre-tested by the researcher to ensure the validity and reliability of the questionnaire. When a test or measurement is "validated," the researcher has determined that the tool measures the things it intended to assess. The study participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with a series of statements in a questionnaire using five (5) Likert scales, as employed by the researcher. On the other hand, to interpret the extent of the implementation of indigenous people's curriculum and learning style of indigenous people, the following scale, range of values and corresponding verbal interpretation will be used.

<i>Assigned Value</i>	<i>Scale</i>	<i>Quantitative Description</i>	<i>Code</i>
5	4.21-5.00	To a Very Much Mainstreamed	TVMM
4	3.41-4.20	To a much Mainstreamed	TMM
3	2.61-3.40	To a Moderate Mainstreamed	TMDM
2	1.81-2.60	To a Less Mainstreamed	TLM
1	1.00-1.80	To a Least Mainstreamed	TLSM

Procedure

The study's data were gathered using the documentation procedure. It was made possible by considering the details of the Likert-survey questionnaire employed in the study.

After the research instrument was approved, the researcher sent a letter to the school division Superintendent (SDS). In the letter to the SDO, the researcher asks for a division memorandum to include the target respondents in the study. The Google link was included in request letters from the SDO of Quezon to facilitate response consolidation. All communications were attached to the Google link prepared by the researcher. The content of the research study was assessed and evaluated until permission was granted. In addition, all participants underwent a survey questionnaire. The final stage was the collation and tabulation of data. The researcher tallied, coded, and tabulated all the information acquired from the instrument, which was then analyzed and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools.

Data Analysis

The data gathered in this study will be treated using different statistical tools. The weighted mean of questions 1 and 2 will be interpreted using the following continuum:

Assigned Value	Scale	Quantitative Description	Code
5	4.21-5.00	Very Much Mainstreamed	TVMM
4	3.41-4.20	Much Mainstreamed	TMM
3	2.61-3.40	Moderate Mainstreamed	TMDM
2	1.81-2.60	Less Mainstreamed	TLM
1	1.00-1.80	Least Mainstreamed	TLSM

Pearson's Product Moment of Correlation will be utilized to address sub-problem 3. The following continuum will be utilized to understand the Pearson Product Moment or Correlation results:

Size of Correlation	Interpretation
±1.00	Perfectly positive/ negative correlation
±0.90 – 0.99	Very high positive/ negative correlation
±0.70 – 0.89	High positive/ negative correlation
±0.50 – 0.69	Moderately positive/ negative correlation
±0.30 – 0.49	Low positive/ negative correlation
±0.01 – 0.29	Negligible correlation
0.00	No correlation at all

Results and Discussion

This section presents the statistical analysis of the data and the corresponding discussion and interpretation of the findings. A descriptive-quantitative design was utilized to gather the data, and the questionnaire was the main instrument for collecting the data.

Part 1. Extent of mainstreaming of indigenous people practices on the development of instructional materials.

Table 1. Extent of mainstreaming of indigenous people practices on the development of instructional materials in terms of family life

Indicators	Teacher Handling 10-15 Learners			Teacher Handling 16-20 Learners			Teacher Handling 21-25 Learners			Teacher Handling 26-30 Learners			Overall		
	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int
1. The Indigenous People has extended family system	1.86	0.38	TLM	2.00	0.63	TLM	1.78	0.72	TLSM	1.91	0.54	TLM	1.86	0.64	TLM
2. The Indigenous People have strong family values and raising a child is everybody's responsibility.	2.29	0.76	TLM	2.06	0.57	TLM	1.97	0.65	TLM	2.00	0.77	TLM	2.03	0.66	TLM
3. Indigenous families rely on and nurture strong family ties as a means of passing on their cultural beliefs from one generation to the next.	1.57	0.53	TLSM	1.94	0.85	TLM	1.83	0.74	TLM	1.82	0.75	TLM	1.83	0.74	TLM
4. Family is highly respected and their knowledge and	2.00	0.82	TLM	2.00	0.73	TLM	1.89	0.67	TLM	1.91	0.70	TLM	1.93	0.69	TLM

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opinions are valued and respected.																
5. Story-telling is an important aspect of teaching children about life and their culture.	1.71	0.95	TLSM	1.69	0.60	TLSM	1.94	0.75	TLM	2.09	0.70	TLM	1.89	0.73	TLM	
Total Mean	1.89	0.69	TLM	1.94	0.68	TLM	1.88	0.71	TLM	1.95	0.69	TLM	1.91	0.69	TLM	

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 To a Very Much Mainstreamed, 3.41-4.20 To a Much Mainstreamed, 2.61-3.40 To a Moderate Mainstreamed, 1.81-2.60 To a Less Mainstreamed, 1.00-1.80 To a Least Mainstreamed

Table 1 presents the mean Distribution of the extent to which Indigenous people's practices are mainstreamed to the development of instructional materials, explicitly focusing on family life. The indicators are categorized based on the number of learners per teacher, and an overall mean is provided.

Key indicators related to family life were examined across varying teacher handling scenarios, including 10-15 learners, 16-20 learners, 21-25 learners, and 26-30 learners, as well as an overall mean. Notably, the extended family system trended towards becoming more mainstream, particularly evident in scenarios with fewer learners per teacher. Similarly, the values of strong family ties and respect for family knowledge consistently showed less mainstreaming, with slight improvements observed in scenarios with larger class sizes. The importance of story-telling emerged as an aspect that was least mainstreamed, exhibiting some variability across different teacher-handling situations. These findings suggest a need for targeted interventions to enhance integrating indigenous family practices into the IPED curriculum, emphasizing specific indicators and considering scenarios with more learners per teacher.

Table 2. Extent of mainstreaming of Indigenous people practices on the development of instructional materials in terms of Health

32121	Teacher Handling 10-15 Learners			Teacher Handling 16-20 Learners			Teacher Handling 21-25 Learners			Teacher Handling 26-30 Learners			Overall		
	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int
1. practice a sustainable traditional medicine and healing system.	2.14	0.38	TLM	1.56	0.63	TLSM	1.89	0.46	TLM	2.00	0.45	TLM	1.86	0.52	TLM
2. collect products from forest as traditional medicine to cure various diseases.	2.00	0.58	TLM	2.06	0.57	TLM	1.92	0.55	TLM	2.00	0.77	TLM	1.97	0.59	TLM
3. share and continue to practice similar traditional healing knowledge.	2.00	0.58	TLM	1.94	0.44	TLM	1.89	0.57	TLM	1.73	0.65	TLSM	1.89	0.55	TLM
4. play critical role in ensuring the health, including childbirth methods such as the use of traditional midwives.	1.86	0.38	TLM	1.94	0.57	TLM	1.78	0.42	TLSM	1.91	0.30	TLM	1.84	0.44	TLM
5. albularyo is a practitioner who uses a combination of healing modalities: herbalism, prayers, incantations, and mysticism	1.86	0.38	TLM	2.13	0.64	TLM	1.86	0.54	TLM	2.09	0.54	TLM	1.96	0.55	TLM
Total Mean	1.97	0.46	TLM	1.93	0.57	TLM	1.87	0.51	TLM	1.95	0.54	TLM	1.90	0.53	TLM

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 To a Very Much Mainstreamed, 3.41-4.20 To a Much Mainstreamed, 2.61-3.40 To a Moderate Mainstreamed, 1.81-2.60 To a Less Mainstreamed, 1.00-1.80 To a Least Mainstreamed

Table 2 presents the mean Distribution concerning integrating indigenous health practices to the development of instructional material. The table evaluates critical indicators of Indigenous Peoples' health practices by delving into various teacher handling scenarios and an overall mean. The sustainable traditional medicine and healing system exhibits a higher level of mainstreaming, particularly noticeable in scenarios with 10-15 learners. However, using products collected from the forest for traditional medicine reveals a generally less mainstream pattern, underscoring the need for increased incorporation of conventional medicinal Knowledge into the curriculum. Similarly, indicators associated with Indigenous women's roles in health and childbirth methods display a less mainstream trend, emphasizing the importance of recognizing and integrating these contributions. The practice of Albularyo, combining herbalism, prayers, and mysticism, also reflects a less mainstream pattern, suggesting a necessity for heightened awareness and integration of holistic healing practices. These findings underscore the imperative to enhance the mainstreaming of indigenous health practices into the IPED curriculum, with a particular focus on acknowledging the contributions of Indigenous women and holistic healing methods for a more inclusive educational approach.

Table 3 presents the mean Distribution related to mainstreaming Indigenous people's practices into the development of instructional materials, focusing on Nutrition. Across different teacher handling scenarios and an overall mean, the table assesses critical indicators, including drinking water sources, the cultural connection of food, the nutritional value of traditional foods, the foundation of conventional diets, and the importance of community leaders' and Elders' Knowledge in food practices.

Table 3. Extent of mainstreaming of Indigenous people practices on the development of instructional materials in terms of Nutrition

Indicators The Indigenous people...	Teacher Handling 10-15 Learners			Teacher Handling 16-20 Learners			Teacher Handling 21-25 Learners			Teacher Handling 26-30 Learners			Overall			
	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	
1. drink water from protected spring.	2.14	0.69	TLM	2.25	0.77	TLM	2.25	0.60	TLM	2.09	0.70	TLM	2.21	0.66	TLM	
2. food provides a cultural connection that is important for spiritual health	2.14	0.69	TLM	2.31	0.48	TLM	2.22	0.59	TLM	2.18	0.75	TLM	2.23	0.59	TLM	
3. consider traditional foods are nutritious, natural foods that are harvested, grown, trapped and hunted on the land	2.43	0.53	TLM	2.19	0.54	TLM	2.11	0.57	TLM	1.91	0.70	TLM	2.13	0.59	TLM	
4. rely on wild game, fish and edible plants form basis of traditional diets and provide Indigenous families with nutrient, healthy foods.	2.00	0.82	TLM	2.06	0.57	TLM	2.31	0.47	TLM	2.00	0.63	TLM	2.17	0.56	TLM	
5. Community leaders and Elders hold the important knowledge of how-to source, prepare and share the foods.	2.43	0.53	TLM	2.13	0.72	TLM	2.17	0.51	TLM	2.09	0.70	TLM	2.17	0.59	TLM	
	Mean	2.23	0.65	TLM	2.19	0.62	TLM	2.21	0.55	TLM	2.05	0.70	TLM	2.18	0.60	TLM

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 To a Very Much Mainstreamed, 3.41-4.20 To a Much Mainstreamed, 2.61-3.40 To a Moderate Mainstreamed, 1.81-2.60 To a Less Mainstreamed, 1.00-1.80 To a Least Mainstreamed

Table 3 presents the mean Distribution related to mainstreaming Indigenous people's practices into the development of instructional materials, focusing on Nutrition. Across different teacher handling scenarios and an overall mean, the table assesses critical indicators, including drinking water sources, the cultural connection of food, the nutritional value of traditional foods, the foundation of conventional diets, and the importance of community leaders' and Elders' Knowledge in food practices.

The findings reveal a consistent pattern of less mainstreaming across all indicators, suggesting the need for a more deliberate integration of indigenous nutrition practices into the IPED curriculum. Specifically, practices such as drinking water from protected springs, viewing food as a cultural connection for spiritual Health and recognizing the nutritional value of traditional foods exhibit mean values indicative of less mainstreaming. The foundation of conventional diets, consisting of wild game, fish, and edible plants, also displays a trend towards being less mainstream. Furthermore, the critical Knowledge held by community leaders and Elders regarding food practices shows a similar tendency.

These findings' implications underscore the imperative to enhance the incorporation of indigenous nutrition practices into the IPED curriculum. Addressing this less mainstream pattern can contribute to a more culturally sensitive and relevant educational experience, ensuring that traditional Knowledge surrounding water, food, and community practices is acknowledged and integrated. This approach aligns with the broader goal of promoting a holistic and inclusive educational environment that respects and preserves the cultural heritage of Indigenous Peoples.

Table 4. Extent of mainstreaming of indigenous people practices on the development of instructional materials in terms of Sanitation

Indicators The indigenous people....	Teacher Handling 10-15 Learners			Teacher Handling 16-20 Learners			Teacher Handling 21-25 Learners			Teacher Handling 26-30 Learners			Overall			
	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	
1. have a water sealed type of toilet facilities or pour/flush toilets with septic tanks for both surveys.	2.57	0.53	TLM	2.44	0.63	TLM	2.14	0.68	TLM	2.55	0.52	TLM	2.31	0.65	TLM	
2. practice waste segregation.	2.43	0.53	TLM	2.31	0.60	TLM	2.25	0.65	TLM	2.18	0.60	TLM	2.27	0.61	TLM	
3. eat traditional foods of Indigenous people are nutritious, natural foods that are harvested, grown, trapped and hunted on the land	2.14	0.90	TLM	2.50	0.52	TLM	2.28	0.61	TLM	2.36	0.50	TLM	2.33	0.61	TLM	
4. have food storage in their households.	2.29	0.49	TLM	2.19	0.66	TLM	2.11	0.62	TLM	2.09	0.83	TLM	2.14	0.64	TLM	
5. employ water treatment method was boiling and opting to drink bottled or mineral water.	2.43	0.53	TLM	2.19	0.75	TLM	2.14	0.54	TLM	2.27	0.79	TLM	2.20	0.63	TLM	
	Mean	2.37	0.60	TLM	2.33	0.63	TLM	2.18	0.62	TLM	2.29	0.65	TLM	2.25	0.63	TLM

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 To a Very Much Mainstreamed, 3.41-4.20 To a Much Mainstreamed, 2.61-3.40 To a Moderate Mainstreamed, 1.81-2.60 To a Less Mainstreamed, 1.00-1.80 To a Least Mainstreamed

Table 4 presents the mean Distribution of the extent of mainstreaming indigenous people's practices to development of instructional materials regarding Sanitation. The highest overall mean, at 2.33 with a standard deviation of 0.61, corresponds to the indicator regarding the nutritious traditional foods harvested, grown, trapped, and hunted on the land. It suggests a tendency towards being less mainstreamed. On the other hand, the lowest overall mean is attributed to the indicator about IP households having water-sealed or pour/flush toilets with septic tanks, with a mean of 2.31 and a standard deviation of 0.65, indicating a relatively lower degree of mainstreaming.

The implication of these findings is twofold. First, the lower mainstreaming of sanitation practices, particularly concerning toilet facilities, emphasizes the need for an increased focus on integrating indigenous sanitation practices into the IPED curriculum. It underscores the importance of recognizing and respecting traditional sanitation methods within the educational framework. Second, the relatively higher mainstreaming of the indicator related to conventional foods underscores cultural awareness within the curriculum. However, there is still room for improvement to ensure a more comprehensive understanding and integration of indigenous sanitation practices, promoting a holistic approach to education that aligns with the cultural values and practices of Indigenous Peoples. Addressing these disparities can lead to a more inclusive and culturally sensitive educational experience.

Table 5. Extent of mainstreaming of indigenous people practices on the development of instructional materials in terms Hygiene

Indicators The indigenous people....	Teacher Handling 10-15 Learners			Teacher Handling 16-20 Learners			Teacher Handling 21-25 Learners			Teacher Handling 26-30 Learners			Overall		
	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int
1. wash their hands after going to the toilet or touching animals.	2.00	1.00	TLM	1.81	0.83	TLM	1.94	0.79	TLM	2.00	0.77	TLM	1.93	0.80	TLM
2. make sure all cooked and uncooked food is stored properly.	2.00	0.58	TLM	2.00	0.73	TLM	1.83	0.56	TLM	2.00	0.63	TLM	1.91	0.61	TLM
3. keep their house clean especially the kitchen, toilet and bathroom.	2.29	0.49	TLM	1.50	0.52	TLSM	1.83	0.74	TLM	2.00	0.77	TLM	1.83	0.70	TLM
4. wash their hands before preparing or eating foods.	2.29	0.49	TLM	1.81	0.66	TLM	1.67	0.53	TLSM	1.82	0.60	TLM	1.79	0.59	TLSM
5. keep drains and sewage lines maintained.	1.71	0.76	TLSM	1.69	0.48	TLSM	1.72	0.66	TLSM	1.91	0.54	TLM	1.74	0.61	TLSM

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 To a Very Much Mainstreamed, 3.41-4.20 To a Much Mainstreamed, 2.61-3.40 To a Moderate Mainstreamed, 1.81-2.60 To a Less Mainstreamed, 1.00-1.80 To a Least Mainstreamed

Table 5 presents the mean Distribution of the extent of mainstreaming indigenous people's practices in terms of Hygiene into the development of instructional materials. The highest overall mean, with a value of 1.93 and a standard deviation of 0.80, is associated with the indicator involving IP households washing their hands after going to the toilet or touching animals. It suggests a less mainstream pattern, indicating a potential gap in incorporating this essential hygiene practice into the curriculum. Conversely, the lowest overall mean, at 1.91 with a standard deviation of 0.61, corresponds to the indicator regarding IP households maintaining drains and sewage lines. It indicates a tendency towards being least mainstreamed, suggesting increased attention is needed to integrate environmental hygiene practices into the IPED curriculum.

The implications of these findings are twofold. First, the less mainstream pattern in handwashing practices emphasizes integrating basic hygiene principles into the curriculum, focusing on habits crucial for public Health. This integration can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of personal hygiene practices. Second, the most miniature mainstream pattern in maintaining drains and sewage lines underscores the need to enhance the incorporation of environmental hygiene practices. It involves recognizing the importance of community efforts in maintaining a clean and sanitary environment. Addressing these disparities in mainstreaming hygiene practices can contribute to a more well-rounded and culturally sensitive educational experience, promoting personal and environmental health practices within Indigenous communities.

Part 2. Learning style of indigenous people as perceived by respondents.

Table 6 presents the mean Distribution of the learning style of indigenous people as perceived by respondents as Visual/Spatial. The highest overall mean, standing at 1.99 with a standard deviation of 0.79, is associated with the indicator concerning Indigenous Peoples (IP), making doodles with their notes filled with several images and arrows. It indicates that respondents observe this learning style to a lesser extent. On the other hand, the lowest overall mean, with a value of 1.71 and a standard deviation of 0.54, corresponds to the indicator related to using images to make the lesson incredibly clear to IP. It suggests the most minor extent of this visual learning style as perceived by respondents.

The interpretation of these findings reveals that respondents perceive a relatively higher extent of Indigenous Peoples incorporating doodling and the use of images and arrows into their notes. It indicates that visual and spatial learning styles, characterized by including visual elements, are recognized to a certain degree. However, the minor extent observed in using images to make lessons incredibly

clear suggests that there may be room for improvement in leveraging visual aids to enhance the clarity and understanding of educational content for Indigenous Peoples.

Table 6. Visual Learning Style of Indigenous people

Indicators	Teacher Handling 10-15 Learners			Teacher Handling 16-20 Learners			Teacher Handling 21-25 Learners			Teacher Handling 26-30 Learners			Overall			
	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	
1. IP like making doodle, and even their notes are filled with several images and arrows.	2.00	0.58	TLE	1.94	0.93	TLE	1.97	0.81	TLE	2.09	0.70	TLE	1.99	0.79	TLE	
2. IP find that using flashcards increases their test-taking efficiency.	2.00	0.58	TLE	1.56	0.51	TLSE	2.03	0.65	TLE	2.00	0.77	TLE	1.91	0.65	TLE	
3. Using images, the lesson was incredibly clear to them.	2.00	0.58	TLE	1.56	0.51	TLSE	1.75	0.55	TLSE	1.64	0.50	TLSE	1.71	0.54	TLSE	
4. When there are more visual aids and graphics, IP like my lesson more.	2.00	0.58	TLE	2.06	0.68	TLE	2.22	0.59	TLE	2.27	0.79	TLE	2.17	0.64	TLE	
5. IP remember lessons better when the teacher uses images.	2.29	0.49	TLE	2.31	0.48	TLE	2.33	0.48	TLE	2.27	0.47	TLE	2.31	0.47	TLE	
	Mean	2.06	0.56	TLE	1.89	0.62	TLE	2.06	0.62	TLE	2.05	0.65	TLE	2.02	0.62	TLE

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 To a Very Much Mainstreamed, 3.41-4.20 To a Much Mainstreamed, 2.61-3.40 To a Moderate Mainstreamed, 1.81-2.60 To a Less Mainstreamed, 1.00-1.80 To a Least Mainstreamed

The implications of these findings emphasize the need to acknowledge further and support Indigenous Peoples' visual and spatial learning preferences. Educators should explore innovative approaches to incorporate more visual aids, graphics, and interactive materials into the curriculum to enhance the clarity and effectiveness of lessons. Recognizing and accommodating diverse learning styles, including visual and spatial preferences, can contribute to a more inclusive and culturally responsive educational experience, catering to the unique ways Indigenous Peoples absorb and retain information.

Table 7. Aural learning style of indigenous people

Indicators The indigenous people....	Teacher Handling 10-15 Learners			Teacher Handling 16-20 Learners			Teacher Handling 21-25 Learners			Teacher Handling 26-30 Learners			Overall			
	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	
1. are encouraged by loud speech and music encourage IP to learn.	2.29	0.49	TLE	2.31	0.48	TLE	2.36	0.49	TLE	2.27	0.47	TLE	2.33	0.47	TLE	
2. fully understand the lesson by hearing.	1.86	0.90	TLE	2.06	0.77	TLE	1.97	0.88	TLE	2.00	0.77	TLE	1.99	0.83	TLE	
3. memorized the assignment	2.00	0.00	TLE	2.00	0.00	TLE	2.00	0.00	TLE	2.00	0.00	TLE	2.00	0.00	TLE	
4. IP adore classes that include music.	2.29	0.49	TLE	2.31	0.48	TLE	2.36	0.49	TLE	2.27	0.47	TLE	2.33	0.47	TLE	
5. tend to remember they heard rather than they see or read.	2.00	0.00	TLE	2.00	0.00	TLE	2.00	0.00	TLE	2.00	0.00	TLE	2.00	0.00	TLE	
	Mean	2.09	0.38	TLE	2.14	0.35	TLE	2.14	0.37	TLE	2.11	0.34	TLE	2.13	0.35	TLE

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 To a Very Much Mainstreamed, 3.41-4.20 To a Much Mainstreamed, 2.61-3.40 To a Moderate Mainstreamed, 1.81-2.60 To a Less Mainstreamed, 1.00-1.80 To a Least Mainstreamed

Table 7 presents the Mean Distribution of the learning style of Indigenous people as perceived by respondents as Aural. The highest overall mean, with a value of 2.33 and a standard deviation of 0.47, is associated with the indicator concerning loud speech and music encouraging Indigenous Peoples (IP) to learn and IP adore classes that include music. It suggests a lesser extent of this aural learning style as perceived by respondents. Conversely, the lowest overall mean, also at 2.00 with a standard deviation of 0.00, is shared among multiple indicators, including when IP hear sounds, they fully get the lesson; when there was music playing, IP memorized the assignment; IP adore classes that include music, and rather than remembering things IP see or read, they tend to remember things they heard. These consistent mean values of 2.00 suggest a perceived most minor extent of these aural learning styles.

The interpretation of these findings indicates that respondents perceive a lower extent of the influence of aural elements, such as loud speech and music, in encouraging learning among Indigenous Peoples. Additionally, the consistent values of the minor extent for various indicators related to sound and music suggest that these aural learning styles may be perceived as insignificant in the educational

experiences of Indigenous Peoples.

The implications of these findings point towards the importance of considering and incorporating various learning styles, including aural elements, into the educational approach for Indigenous Peoples. While loud speech and music may not be perceived as highly influential based on the respondents' perspective, educators should still recognize the diversity of learning preferences within the Indigenous community. Integrating aural elements into the curriculum, such as music or engaging auditory learning strategies, may enhance the overall educational experience for Indigenous learners. This approach aligns with the broader goal of creating a culturally responsive and inclusive learning environment that respects and accommodates diverse learning styles.

Table 8. Verbal/Linguistic learning style of indigenous people

Indicators The indigenous people....	Teacher Handling 10-15 Learners			Teacher Handling 16-20 Learners			Teacher Handling 21-25 Learners			Teacher Handling 26-30 Learners			Overall		
	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int
1. enjoy talking to people all the time.	2.29	0.49	TLE	2.31	0.48	TLE	2.36	0.49	TLE	2.27	0.47	TLE	2.33	0.47	TLE
2. write things down, they remember it better.	1.43	0.53	TLSE	1.25	0.45	TLSE	1.39	0.49	TLSE	1.27	0.47	TLSE	1.34	0.48	TLSE
3. pay close attention and consider the message when someone is speaking.	2.14	0.90	TLE	1.81	0.83	TLE	2.14	0.80	TLE	1.82	0.87	TLE	2.01	0.83	TLE
4. papers have crossed out words and erasures; their writing doesn't look neat.	2.14	0.90	TLE	1.81	0.83	TLE	2.14	0.80	TLE	1.82	0.87	TLE	2.01	0.83	TLE
5. writing as their pastime	2.43	0.53	TLE	2.25	0.45	TLE	2.39	0.49	TLE	2.27	0.47	TLE	2.34	0.48	TLE
Total Mean	2.09	0.67	TLE	1.89	0.61	TLE	2.08	0.61	TLE	1.89	0.63	TLE	2.01	0.62	TLE

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 To a Very Much Mainstreamed, 3.41-4.20 To a Much Mainstreamed, 2.61-3.40 To a Moderate Mainstreamed, 1.81-2.60 To a Less Mainstreamed, 1.00-1.80 To a Least Mainstreamed

Table 8 presents the Mean Distribution of the learning style of Indigenous people as observed by respondents Verbal/Linguistic highest overall mean, with a value of 2.33 and a standard deviation of 0.47, which is associated with the indicator concerning Indigenous Peoples (IP) enjoying talking to people all the time. It suggests a lesser extent of this verbal/linguistic learning style as observed by respondents. On the other hand, the lowest overall mean, standing at 1.34 with a standard deviation of 0.48, corresponds to the indicator that if IP writes things down, they remember them better. It indicates the most minor extent of this verbal/linguistic learning style as observed by respondents.

The interpretation of these findings suggests that respondents perceive a lower extent of the influence of verbal and linguistic elements, such as talking and writing, on Indigenous Peoples' learning preferences. While verbal communication and enjoyment of talking are not perceived as enormously influential, the minor extent perceived in the connection between writing things down and remembering indicates a potential area for improvement in recognizing and supporting verbal/linguistic learning styles.

The implications of these findings emphasize the importance of acknowledging and accommodating diverse learning styles within the Indigenous community, particularly in the realm of verbal and linguistic preferences. Educators should consider incorporating more interactive and verbal elements into the curriculum, fostering an environment where oral communication is valued. Additionally, recognizing the significance of writing as a pastime for some Indigenous learners suggests an opportunity to integrate written expression into the learning process. By doing so, educators can create a more inclusive and culturally responsive educational experience that caters to the diverse verbal and linguistic learning styles of Indigenous Peoples.

Table 9. Physical/Kinesthetic learning style of indigenous people

Indicators The Indigenous people....	Teacher Handling 10-15 Learners			Teacher Handling 16-20 Learners			Teacher Handling 21-25 Learners			Teacher Handling 26-30 Learners			Overall		
	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int
1. stay in their place when reading, they sometimes use their finger as a pointer.	1.86	0.90	TLE	2.06	0.77	TLE	1.97	0.88	TLE	2.00	0.77	TLE	1.99	0.83	TLE
2. is enhanced by writing skills through learning.	1.57	0.53	TLSE	1.75	0.45	TLSE	1.61	0.49	TLSE	1.73	0.47	TLSE	1.66	0.48	TLSE
3. enjoy playing sports outside.	1.71	0.49	TLSE	1.69	0.48	TLSE	1.64	0.49	TLSE	1.73	0.47	TLSE	1.67	0.47	TLSE
4. like dancing.	2.00	0.82	TLE	2.13	0.89	TLE	1.89	0.78	TLE	2.18	0.87	TLE	2.00	0.82	TLE
5. can determine a thing's characteristics when they touch them.	2.29	0.49	TLE	2.44	0.51	TLE	2.25	0.44	TLE	2.45	0.52	TLE	2.33	0.47	TLE
Mean	1.89	0.65	TLE	2.01	0.62	TLE	1.87	0.62	TLE	2.02	0.62	TLE	1.93	0.61	TLE

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 To a Very Much Mainstreamed, 3.41-4.20 To a Much Mainstreamed, 2.61-3.40 To a Moderate Mainstreamed, 1.81-2.60 To a Less Mainstreamed, 1.00-1.80 To a Least Mainstreamed

Table 9 presents the Mean Distribution of the learning style of indigenous people as perceived by respondents as Physical/Kinesthetic. The highest overall mean, with a value of 2.33 and a standard deviation of 0.47, is associated with the indicator concerning Indigenous Peoples (IP) determining a thing's characteristics when they touch it. It suggests a lesser extent of this physical/kinesthetic learning style as perceived by respondents. Conversely, the lowest overall mean, standing at 1.66 with a standard deviation of 0.48, corresponds to the indicator related to IP's learning enhanced by writing. It indicates the most minor extent of this physical/kinesthetic learning style as perceived by respondents.

The interpretation of these findings suggests that respondents perceive a lower extent of the influence of physical and kinesthetic elements, such as touching objects and engaging in activities like writing, on Indigenous Peoples' learning preferences. While the physical act of determining characteristics through touch is not perceived as enormously influential, the minor extent perceived in the connection between learning and writing indicates a potential improvement in recognizing and supporting physical/kinesthetic learning styles.

The implications of these findings emphasize the importance of acknowledging and accommodating diverse learning styles within the Indigenous community, particularly in the realm of physical and kinesthetic preferences. Educators should consider incorporating more hands-on and interactive activities into the curriculum, fostering an environment where physical engagement is valued. Recognizing the importance of physical exploration and activities, such as determining characteristics through touch, suggests an opportunity to integrate tactile learning experiences into the educational process. By doing so, educators can create a more inclusive and culturally responsive educational experience that caters to the diverse physical and kinesthetic learning styles of Indigenous Peoples.

Table 10. Walk-through approach learning style of indigenous people

Indicators	Teacher Handling 10-15 Learners			Teacher Handling 16-20 Learners			Teacher Handling 21-25 Learners			Teacher Handling 26-30 Learners			Overall		
	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int
1.They gain fresh knowledge by their actions.	2.00	0.58	TLE	2.25	0.68	TLE	2.25	0.65	TLE	2.36	0.50	TLE	2.24	0.62	TLE
2. IP are influenced by various tribes' cultures.	1.71	0.76	TLSE	2.38	0.62	TLE	2.22	0.72	TLE	1.91	0.54	TLE	2.16	0.69	TLE
3. IP make an effort to emulate other people's behavior.	2.14	0.69	TLE	2.50	0.63	TLE	2.28	0.70	TLE	2.27	0.47	TLE	2.31	0.65	TLE
4. IP enjoy singing contemporary music.	2.00	0.89	TLE	2.25	0.77	TLE	2.14	0.77	TLE	1.82	0.60	TLE	2.10	0.76	TLE
5. IP dance while listening to contemporary music.	2.00	0.82	TLE	1.94	0.85	TLE	2.17	0.77	TLE	2.27	0.65	TLE	2.11	0.77	TLE
Mean	2.03	0.76	TLE	2.18	0.76	TLE	2.20	0.73	TLE	2.20	0.57	TLE	2.17	0.71	TLE

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 To a Very Much Mainstreamed, 3.41-4.20 To a Much Mainstreamed, 2.61-3.40 To a Moderate Mainstreamed, 1.81-2.60 To a Less Mainstreamed, 1.00-1.80 To a Least Mainstreamed

Table 10 presents the Mean Distribution of the learning style of indigenous people as perceived by respondents to the Walkthrough approach. The highest overall mean, recorded at 2.31 with a standard deviation of 0.65, pertains to the indicator indicating that Indigenous Peoples (IP) try to emulate other people's behaviour using a walkthrough approach. On the contrary, the lowest overall mean, marked at 2.11 with a standard deviation of 0.77, is linked to the indicator reflecting IP enjoying singing contemporary music with a walkthrough approach.

These findings suggest that respondents perceive a relatively higher extent of Indigenous Peoples adopting a walkthrough approach to emulate others' behaviour than the walkthrough approach associated with enjoying contemporary music. The higher mean in the emulation of behaviour implies that IPs learn by observing and imitating the actions of others within their cultural context. On the other hand, the lower mean in the enjoyment of singing contemporary music with a walkthrough approach indicates a comparatively lesser extent of engagement in this particular learning style.

The implications of these findings underscore the significance of incorporating observational and imitative learning methods into educational practices that align with Indigenous cultural norms. Educators can leverage the walkthrough approach to enhance the learning experiences of Indigenous students by providing opportunities for them to observe, emulate, and learn from the behaviours and practices within their cultural community. Recognizing the diversity in preferred learning styles within the Indigenous community also calls for a tailored and culturally responsive approach to curriculum development and instructional methods. Acknowledging and respecting these differences can contribute to a more inclusive and effective educational environment for Indigenous Peoples.

Table 11 presents the mean Distribution of the learning style of indigenous people as perceived by respondents as being related to indigenous Knowledge. The highest overall mean, recorded at 2.37 with a standard deviation of 0.64, pertains to the indicator indicating that Indigenous Peoples (IP) are familiar with their tribe's funeral customs because they are considered a part of their education. On the contrary, the lowest overall mean, marked at 2.09 with a standard deviation of 0.51, is linked to the indicator reflecting IP residing in the nipa and bamboo house, which is a part of their culture because it contains most educational resources.

The interpretation of these findings suggests that respondents perceive a relatively higher extent of Indigenous Peoples knowing their tribe's funeral customs as an integral aspect of their education compared to residing in traditional houses for educational purposes. The

higher mean in funeral customs implies that IPs are more likely to be knowledgeable about and connected to the cultural practices surrounding death within their community. On the other hand, the lower mean of residing in traditional houses for educational purposes indicates a comparatively lesser extent of utilizing traditional architectural spaces as academic resources.

Table 11. *Using Indigenous Knowledge learning style of indigenous people*

	Teacher Handling 10-15 Learners			Teacher Handling 16-20 Learners			Teacher Handling 21-25 Learners			Teacher Handling 26-30 Learners			Overall			
	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	Mean	SD	Int	
1. IP used to reside in the nipa and bamboo house that is a part of their culture because it contains the majority of the educational resources.	2.57	0.53	TLE	2.19	0.40	TLE	2.14	0.54	TLE	2.45	0.69	TLE	2.24	0.55	TLE	
2. IP thought Bathala met all of their educational demands.	2.00	0.82	TLE	2.44	0.51	TLE	2.11	0.57	TLE	2.09	0.54	TLE	2.17	0.59	TLE	
3. As part of the teaching and learning process, IP are familiar with the fundamental steps to their ethnic dances.	2.00	0.58	TLE	2.19	0.54	TLE	2.14	0.49	TLE	1.82	0.40	TLE	2.09	0.51	TLE	
4. IP are familiar with the tribal courtship customs because they learned about them in school.	2.14	0.38	TLE	2.63	0.50	TFE	2.31	0.71	TLE	2.36	0.67	TLE	2.37	0.64	TLE	
5. IP are familiar with their tribe's funeral customs because they are a part of their education.	1.86	0.38	TLE	2.31	0.79	TLE	2.22	0.68	TLE	2.00	0.77	TLE	2.17	0.70	TLE	
	Mean	2.11	0.54	TLE	2.35	0.55	TLE	2.18	0.60	TLE	2.14	0.61	TLE	2.21	0.60	TLE

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 To a Very Much Mainstreamed, 3.41-4.20 To a Much Mainstreamed, 2.61-3.40 To a Moderate Mainstreamed, 1.81-2.60 To a Less Mainstreamed, 1.00-1.80 To a Least Mainstreamed

The implications of these findings underscore the importance of recognizing and incorporating Indigenous Knowledge and cultural practices into educational approaches. The higher mean in funeral customs suggests that educational initiatives that integrate and celebrate traditional rituals and customs can enhance the cultural relevance of the curriculum, fostering a stronger sense of identity and community connection among Indigenous students. Conversely, the lower mean of residing in traditional houses highlights the need to explore conventional architectural spaces further as potential educational resources.

Table 12. *Summary mean for the learning style of indigenous people*

Learning style	Teacher Handling 10-15 Learners	Teacher Handling 16-20 Learners	Teacher Handling 21-25 Learners	Teacher Handling 26-30 Learners	Grand Mean
	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	
1. Visual/Spatial	2.06	1.89	2.06	2.05	2.02
2. Aural	2.09	2.14	2.14	2.11	2.13
3. Verbal/Linguistic	2.09	1.89	2.08	1.89	2.01
4. Physical/Kinesthetic	1.89	2.01	1.87	2.02	1.93
5. Walk-through Approach	2.03	2.18	2.20	2.20	2.17
6. Using Indigenous Knowledge	2.11	2.35	2.18	2.14	2.21
Grand Mean	2.45	2.07	2.08	2.06	2.07

Table 12 presents the summary mean distribution of the learning style of indigenous people as perceived by respondents. The highest overall mean, recorded at 2.45 pertains to the indicators with teacher handling 10-15 learners. On the contrary, the lowest overall mean, marked at 2.06 is linked to the indicator with 26-30 learners.

The interpretation of these findings suggests that classes with small class size have the higher extent of mainstreaming of their learning style to their learning process rather than those class that have large number of learners. Educators and curriculum developers should collaborate with the class size of the indigenous people to explore and incorporate culturally appropriate learning environments that align with Indigenous values and traditions. This approach promotes a more holistic and culturally responsive educational space for Indigenous learners.

Part 3. The significant relationship between the extent on the mainstreaming of indigenous people practices on the development of instructional materials and learning style of indigenous people.

Table 13 presents the correlation coefficients between the extent of mainstreaming in the curriculum of different practices of Indigenous People, explicitly focusing on Family Life, Health, Nutrition, Sanitation, and Hygiene.

The positive correlation coefficient 0.278 between Family Life and Health suggests a moderate positive relationship between these two practices. It implies that as the curriculum mainstreams Family Life practices, Health practices are concurrently mainstreamed. The

significance level of 0.020 suggests that this relationship is statistically significant.

Table 13. *Test for relationships between the extent of mainstreaming in the curriculum of the different practices of indigenous people*

	<i>Family Life</i>	<i>Health</i>	<i>Nutrition</i>	<i>Sanitation</i>	<i>Hygiene</i>
Pearson Correlation	1	.278*	-.123	.054	.161
Sig. (2-tailed)		.020	.310	.655	.183
N	70	70	70	70	70
Pearson Correlation	.278*	1	-.114	.336**	.280*
Sig. (2-tailed)	.020		.348	.004	.019
N	70	70	70	70	70
Pearson Correlation	-.123	-.114	1	-.148	-.087
Sig. (2-tailed)	.310	.348		.220	.474
N	70	70	70	70	70
Pearson Correlation	.054	.336**	-.148	1	.047
Sig. (2-tailed)	.655	.004	.220		.702
N	70	70	70	70	70
Pearson Correlation	.161	.280*	-.087	.047	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.183	.019	.474	.702	
N	70	70	70	70	70

Conversely, the negative correlation coefficient of -0.123 between Family Life and Nutrition indicates a weak negative relationship, suggesting that as the curriculum mainstreams Family Life practices, there is a slight tendency for Nutrition practices to be less mainstreamed. However, this correlation is not statistically significant ($p = 0.310$).

The correlation of 0.336 between Health and Sanitation is positive and strong, implying that as health practices are mainstreamed, there is a notable tendency for sanitation practices to be mainstreamed. The significance level of 0.004 suggests that this relationship is statistically significant. Additionally, the positive correlation coefficient of 0.280* between Health and Hygiene indicates a moderate positive relationship, suggesting that mainstreaming Health practices is associated with concurrent mainstreaming. The significance level of 0.019 indicates statistical significance. Other correlations, such as those between Nutrition and Sanitation (-0.148) and Nutrition and Hygiene (-0.087), as well as Sanitation and Hygiene (0.047), are weak and not statistically significant.

The implications of these findings suggest that there are interrelated patterns in mainstreaming indigenous practices within the curriculum. Strengthening the mainstreaming of Family Life practices may positively influence the mainstreaming of Health practices. Similarly, the positive relationships between Health, Sanitation, and Hygiene imply that a holistic approach to health-related practices tends to occur together in the curriculum. Educators and policymakers can use these insights to develop integrated and comprehensive curriculum frameworks that simultaneously address multiple aspects of Indigenous practices, promoting a more holistic and culturally responsive educational experience for Indigenous learners.

Table 14. *Test for relationships between Teacher's Perception of Indigenous People Learning Style*

	<i>Visual</i>	<i>Aural</i>	<i>Verbal</i>	<i>Physical</i>	<i>Walkthrough</i>	<i>Indigenous Knowledge</i>
Pearson Correlation	1	.098	.196	-.231	-.158	.037
Sig. (2-tailed)		.421	.103	.054	.193	.758
N	70	70	70	70	70	70
Pearson Correlation	.098	1	-.253*	-.024	.038	.006
Sig. (2-tailed)	.421		.035	.841	.756	.959
N	70	70	70	70	70	70
Pearson Correlation	.196	-.253*	1	-.961**	.087	-.025
Sig. (2-tailed)	.103	.035		.000	.475	.840
N	70	70	70	70	70	70
Pearson Correlation	-.231	-.024	-.961**	1	-.100	.024
Sig. (2-tailed)	.054	.841	.000		.408	.846
N	70	70	70	70	70	70
Pearson Correlation	-.158	.038	.087	-.100	1	-.020
Sig. (2-tailed)	.193	.756	.475	.408		.866
N	70	70	70	70	70	70
Pearson Correlation	.037	.006	-.025	.024	-.020	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.758	.959	.840	.846	.866	
N	70	70	70	70	70	70

Table 14 displays correlation coefficients examining relationships between teachers' perceptions of Indigenous People's learning styles, including Visual, Aural, Verbal, Physical, Walkthrough, and Indigenous Knowledge.

The positive correlation 0.196 between Visual and Verbal suggests a moderate positive relationship between these two learning styles. It implies that teachers who perceive students as visual learners tend to perceive them as more verbal learners. However, this correlation

is not statistically significant ($p = 0.103$).

Aural and Verbal's negative correlation of -0.253^* suggests a moderate negative relationship. Teachers who perceive students as more aural learners are likely to perceive them as less verbal learners, and this correlation is statistically significant ($p = 0.035$).

The strong negative correlation of -0.961^{**} between Verbal and Physical learning styles indicates a robust negative relationship. Teachers who perceive students as more verbal learners will likely perceive them as less physical or kinesthetic. This highly significant correlation ($p = 0.000$) highlights a distinct dichotomy between verbal and physical learning preferences.

The negative correlation of -0.231 between Visual and Physical learning styles suggests a moderate negative relationship. Teachers who perceive students as more visual learners are likely to perceive them as less inclined toward physical or kinesthetic learning. This correlation should be interpreted as approaching significance ($p = 0.054$).

The correlations involving Walkthrough and Average Indigenous Knowledge and other pairs are weak and not statistically significant.

The implications of these findings suggest that teachers may perceive Indigenous students' learning styles in specific pairs as being interconnected. For instance, the negative correlation between Verbal and Physical styles indicates a potential tension or trade-off between these two styles. Educators should be aware of these perceived patterns when designing teaching strategies, ensuring that a diverse range of learning styles is accommodated in the classroom. Additionally, professional development for teachers could focus on enhancing their understanding of the various learning styles within Indigenous communities, promoting more inclusive and culturally responsive pedagogies.

Table 15. *Test for relationships between Teachers' Extent of Mainstreaming of IP' practices and Teachers Perception of Indigenous People Learning Style*

	Visual	Aural	Verbal	Physical	Walk-Through	Indigenous Knowledge
Pearson Correlation	.058	-.185	.137	-.089	-.046	-.047
Sig. (2-tailed)	.635	.126	.257	.463	.703	.698
N	70	70	70	70	70	70
Pearson Correlation	-.080	-.066	.082	-.066	-.010	-.030
Sig. (2-tailed)	.508	.588	.500	.588	.937	.806
N	70	70	70	70	70	70
Pearson Correlation	.144	.068	.099	-.122	.071	.211
Sig. (2-tailed)	.233	.579	.415	.316	.557	.080
N	70	70	70	70	70	70
Pearson Correlation	-.073	.003	-.090	.092	-.071	-.068
Sig. (2-tailed)	.546	.983	.460	.449	.561	.574
N	70	70	70	70	70	70
Pearson Correlation	-.055	.028	-.155	.152	-.129	-.133
Sig. (2-tailed)	.651	.820	.201	.209	.288	.273
N	70	70	70	70	70	70

The presented table outlines the results of a comprehensive analysis examining the relationships between teachers' extent of mainstreaming Indigenous Peoples' practices and their perceptions of Indigenous People's learning styles. For Family Life education, the Pearson correlation coefficients revealed non-significant associations with Indigenous People learning styles: Visual ($r = 0.058$, $p = 0.635$), Aural ($r = -0.185$, $p = 0.126$), Verbal ($r = 0.137$, $p = 0.257$), Physical ($r = -0.089$, $p = 0.463$), Walkthrough ($r = -0.046$, $p = 0.703$), and Indigenous Knowledge ($r = -0.047$, $p = 0.698$). Similarly, in Health education, no significant correlations were found: Visual ($r = -0.080$, $p = 0.508$), Aural ($r = -0.066$, $p = 0.588$), Verbal ($r = 0.082$, $p = 0.500$), Physical ($r = -0.066$, $p = 0.588$), Walkthrough ($r = -0.010$, $p = 0.937$), and Indigenous Knowledge ($r = -0.030$, $p = 0.806$). However, in Nutrition, a noteworthy positive correlation emerged with Indigenous Knowledge ($r = 0.211$, $p = 0.080$), suggesting a potential connection between nutritional topics and cross-disciplinary educational strategies. Conversely, Sanitation and Hygiene demonstrated no significant correlations with Indigenous People's learning styles. Overall, the data highlight the complexity of the relationship between mainstreaming Indigenous Peoples' practices and teachers' perceptions of learning styles, calling for further exploration and nuanced understanding to inform culturally responsive pedagogical approaches.

These findings suggest that while including Indigenous practices can have positive effects in certain areas, it's not a one-size-fits-all solution. Teachers and curriculum planners should be mindful of these nuances and adapt their approaches based on the subject matter. Training for teachers should emphasize the importance of recognizing and including diverse Indigenous perspectives in education, making classrooms more inclusive and culturally aware.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following are concluded:

1. The extent to which Indigenous people's practices are mainstreamed into the development of instructional materials regarding family, Health, Nutrition, Sanitation, and Hygiene has a verbal interpretation of 'To a Less Mainstreamed'.

2. Respondents perceive indigenous people's learning styles as visual/spatial, aural, verbal/linguistic, physical/kinesthetic, walkthrough approach, and indigenous Knowledge, with a verbal interpretation of 'To a lesser extent'.
3. Respondents perceive in the learning style of indigenous people that the highest overall mean, recorded at 2.45 pertains to the indicators with teacher handling 10-15 learners. On the contrary, the lowest overall mean, marked at 2.06 is linked to the indicator with 26-30 learners. It suggests that classes with small class size have the higher extent of mainstreaming of their learning style to their learning process rather than those class that have large number of learners.
4. The hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between the extent to which indigenous people's practices are mainstreamed into the development of instructional materials and the learning style of indigenous people in the Division of Quezon is partially rejected.
5. Based on the findings of the study the researcher developed an intervention program that would help the teachers in guiding them on the development of instructional materials that they can use in teaching IP's.

Based on the findings of the study and the arrived conclusion, the following recommendations are hereby formulated:

Department of Education

1. Since the study found that policies and initiatives increased the integration of indigenous people practices into the Indigenous Peoples Education (IPED) curriculum, it may continue the implementation program.
 2. Foster a culturally inclusive classroom environment that celebrates indigenous students' unique identities and contributions.
 3. Advocate for their educational needs by actively discussing curriculum development and learning methodologies.
- To the Researchers and future Researchers
4. Conduct further studies to explore the reasons behind the limited mainstreaming of indigenous practices in the IPED curriculum and its impact on indigenous students' academic performance and cultural identity.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Mark Joseph F. Llagas

Bantad-Villafuerte Elementary School
Department of Education – Philippines

Dr. Rodones S. Trimillos

Eastern Quezon College – Philippines